

Optimisation of operational parameters in laboratory-scale enzymatic protein hydrolysis of fishery waste for biostimulant production

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Abstract

The global fish production sector is crucial for food security, employment, and economic sustainability, with projected growth to 204 million tonnes by 2030. However, significant waste (25-30% of biomass) is produced, leading to environmental concerns and disposal costs. This study explores enzymatic protein hydrolysis (EPH) as a sustainable method for recovering valuable biomolecules from fish and mollusc waste, contributing to a circular economy. Various operational parameters, including temperature, pH, enzyme type, hydrolysis duration, enzyme-to-substrate ratio, and substrate dilution, were investigated to optimise nitrogen recovery (NR) and crude protein (CP) yield. The results showed that most CP recovery occurred within the first four hours. Alcalase® at 60°C demonstrated enhanced NR compared to Protana Prime®, while pH adjustments had minimal impact, reducing the need for chemical control. A 1:1 substrate-to-water ratio resulted in a similar NR as that of 1:2 with reduced water quantity, and halving the enzyme dosage achieved comparable recovery, leading to cost savings. These findings suggest the potential for scaling up to pilot and industrial levels, with significant savings in energy, water, chemicals, and enzyme use. Future studies should assess biostimulant efficacy and economic feasibility at a larger scale.

Keywords

Biostimulant, Circular economy, Enzymatic protein hydrolysis, Fishery waste, Hydrolysates, Waste valorisation

INTRODUCTION

Fish production reached 185 million tonnes (Mt) in 2022 and is expected to reach 204 Mt by 2030. The sector plays a significant role in ensuring food security through nutrient supply and healthy human diet, employment and substantial economic contribution with an estimated market value of USD 452 billion with 65.5% from the aquaculture sector. Although serves as the backbone of social and economic sustainability, efforts are necessary to transform the sector into a sustainable one to achieve the sustainable development goals of 2030 (FAO, 2024). While a major proportion of the fish is destined for human consumption, according to Bruno et al., (2019) around 25-30% of fish waste is generated from fishery biomass. This matrix is highly putrescible and demands urgent measures to avoid adverse environmental and health issues and to comply with stringent regulations such as EU 1069/2009 implementing rules on use and disposal of animal-based waste and their derived products. This increases the processing facility's operational costs to ensure proper disposal of these wastes. Fish waste can have substantial economic potential as these byproducts contain various biomolecules like vitamins, proteins, lipids, polysaccharides and minerals. Recovery of these biomolecules can lead to a circular economy approach in the seafood sector by closing the nutrient loop and mitigating environmental effects.

In this regard, Andreola et al., (2023) proposed a biorefinery scheme with techno-economic assessment for seafood byproducts into valuable bioproducts incorporating composting, enzymatic protein hydrolysis, pyrolysis and a liming agent from dried shellfish shells.

The study aims to evaluate the effects of operational parameters of the enzymatic hydrolysis process at a laboratory scale (pH, temperature, best-performing enzyme, hydrolysis duration, enzyme-to-

substrate ratio, and substrate-to-water ratio) on nitrogen recovery to optimise the hydrolysis process by reducing enzymes, water, energy demands and chemicals addition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mollusc and fish waste collection

Mollusc (M) and fish (F) waste were collected from local processing facilities based in Ancona, Italy.

Pretreatments

Fish waste (comprising heads, viscera, bones and scales) was minced with meat mincer to homogenise its composition. Mollusc waste was ground with a shredding pump to separate meat and shell fraction and tap water (W) was added to the mollusc in 1:3(kg/kg).

Lab scale tests

Enzymatic protein hydrolysis (EPH) tests were conducted in 1-litre borosilicate beakers placed in a thermoregulated bath set to the desired temperature for the hydrolysis reaction. An overhead stirrer was mounted onto the beaker to ensure mixing at 200rpm. Enzymes were added at a specific substrate-to-enzyme ratio (v: w).

For pH-controlled tests, a 3M NaOH solution was manually dosed to maintain a stable pH, which was monitored hourly using a pH probe. Commercially available enzymes, Protana Prime® and Alcalase® Pure 4.0 L (Novozymes) were used. The tests were conducted in duplicate, with test time ranging between 4 and 6 hours.

Endogenous enzymes were inactivated before the hydrolysis reaction by heating the samples at 100°C for 10 minutes on a heating plate, and cooling to room temperature unless otherwise specified. After the end of hydrolysis, the samples were again heated at 100°C for 10 minutes to deactivate the enzymes. Samples were collected every 2 hours and centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 30 minutes. Blank tests were performed by deactivation of endogenous enzymes in the substrate and without the addition of commercial enzymes.

Analytical methods

Samples were analysed for total solids (TS) and moisture content (MC) according to UNI EN 13040:2002. Total volatile solids (TVS) were determined using the 209D method (WEF and AWWA, 1998), while total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) was measured using the UNI EN 15604:2009 procedure. Crude protein content was estimated by multiplying TKN by a factor of 6.25 (AOAC, 1997). Electrical conductivity (EC) was assessed using a conductivity probe on the liquid fraction. Soluble protein content was quantified using the Lowry et al. (1951) method. Nitrogen recovery was calculated as the ratio of TKN in the centrifuged liquid to TKN in the substrate, expressed as a percentage. Hydrolysate yield was calculated by the ratio of the weight of liquid hydrolysate to the weight of both liquid and solid fractions, expressed as a percentage.

Influence of Process Parameters

Tests were performed using univariate analysis to evaluate their effects on nitrogen recovery in final hydrolysates while optimising hydrolysis conditions to lower energy, water, enzymes and chemical usage. In the first phase, three different temperatures (28, 40 and 60°C) and two different enzyme performances were tested, then in the second phase three different pH's (no control, 7.5 and 8.5), and in subsequent phases substrate to water, enzymes to substrate ratio, the synergy of endogenous enzymes with commercial enzymes, and finally hydrolysis duration of 4 and 6 hours were tested.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Substrate characteristics

Fish, mollusc meat and their mix (1:1 w/w) were functionally characterised as reported in Table 1. It was observed that fish waste had higher TVS, nitrogen, and carbon content compared to mollusc waste. However, mollusc waste had higher MC than fish as it contained added water (1:3 w/w, S:W) at pretreatment to separate meat fractions. Mix substrate had characteristics as intermediate between fish and mollusc waste, as expected.

Table 1 Characterisation of substrates

Substrate type	MC%	TS (%)	TVS (%)	C (%TS)	N (%TS)	C/N
Fish (n=8)	74.2 ±4.7	25.8 ±4.7	86.2 ±3	47.1±1.6	7.5 ±1.8	6.3
Mollusc (n= 3)	90.8±4.5	9.2±4.5	45.5±16.9	24.9±9.3	4.6±1.8	5.4
Mix (n=3) (M: W: F = 1:2:1)	84.1±1.7	15.9±1.7	58.1±1	31.7±0.5	5.5±1.8	5.8

Duration of Hydrolysis

In terms of crude protein recovery, it was observed for exogenous enzymes that most of the recovery occurred in 4 hours and afterwards, the recovery rate was constant. This is a potential indication that the hydrolysis concludes in 4 to 6 hours, and the long duration does not show efficiency from an operational cost basis.

Effects of Enzymes and Temperature

Obvious differences were observed for different enzymes in nitrogen recovery (NR) at three tested temperatures (Table 2). Alcalase resulted in higher NR compared to Protana Prime[®] and blank test, particularly at 60°C. NR for Protana Prime[®] for various substrates was 13-28% higher than blank tests. It can be seen that NR exceeded 100% attributable to sample concentration due to evaporation. Thus, the following tests were performed by covering vessels. Moreover, fish substrate resulted in higher nitrogen recovery for alcalase at 60°C. This indicated the efficiency of the Alcalase[®] enzyme at 60 °C and therefore was adopted for subsequent test of parameters effects evaluation.

Table 2 Nitrogen recovery using different enzymes at three temperatures

Enzyme	60°C			40°C			28°C		
	F	M	Mix	F	M	Mix	F	M	Mix
Alcalase	106	76	102	39	97	111	50	51	55
Protana	13	26	28	1	17	-1	-4	3	-7

pH control effect

Different pH values (no control, 7.5 and 8.5) did not result in significant NR differences for all the substrates at 60°C and 4 hours of hydrolysis duration. Based on these observations, it was decided to not control pH even though literature studies adjusted, lowering chemical costs (Camargo et al., 2021, Vazquez et al., 2020).

Substrate dilution effect

Dilution effects were assessed for fish and mix substrates comparing NR and CR at two dilution ratios (1:1 and 1:2 w/w). It resulted that 1:1 resulted in CR possibly due to concentrated substrate, however, in terms of NR, 1:2 dilution showed efficiency for both fish and mixed substrates. It is therefore a compromise between the slight product efficiency and operational costs as high quantity of water addition and the subsequent need for concentration of final liquid hydrolysates to concentrate the nitrogen content.

Endogenous and Alcalase enzyme synergy

To assess endogenous enzyme synergy with Alcalase[®] (E:S = 1:100 v/w), fish and mixed substrates were hydrolysed at 4 and 6 hours at 60 °C and compared with alcalase enzyme in terms of NR. It resulted in endogenous plus Alcalase[®] enzymes slightly improving NR as opposed to Alcalase[®] enzymes only at 4 hours for both substrates. While 6 hours of hydrolysis showed slightly more (~3%) than 4 hours. It may suggest some synergistic effect of the endogenous enzyme with alcalase, potentially resulting in lower energy demands required for deactivating endogenous enzymes before the start of hydrolysis.

Enzyme-to-substrate ratio (E:S)

E:S ratios of 1:100 and 1:200 were assessed for fish and mix substrates at 6 hours to evaluate their effectiveness in NR and CR. Fish resulted in faster CR recovery than mixed substrates, while NR was comparable for 1:100 and 1:200 ratios for both substrates. NR was higher for the 1:100 than the 1:200 ratio. While studies showed that an increase in enzyme concentration results in an improved degree of hydrolysis (Vazquez et al., 2020) and nitrogen recovery (Benjakul & Morrissey, 1997). The presented results suggest that nearly similar results can be obtained with half enzyme dosages saving on considerable operational costs. However, biostimulant and pot trials are necessary to confirm how different dosages affect the efficiency of the biostimulant.

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